

“Here’s strangeness.” A Collaborative Approach to Visualising Textual Variation

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“My machine doesn't just analyze and spit out results. All it says is, ‘Here is strangeness.’ I’m the one who gets to look” (Zalewski 1997). When interviewed about the McLoad Portable Collator, a peculiar contraption he fabricated to compare two versions of a text and detect the differences between them, Randall McLoad perfectly summarized the merits of using a tool to study textual variation: in addition to neatly computing the difference between two or more versions, a comparison tool can draw attention to certain locations in the text that merit closer inspection.

Collation, i.e., this act of comparing two or more versions of a text and mapping the variation between them, is a trusted methodology in textual scholarship. It’s used to track the transmission of manuscripts, to study the development of a literary work, or to construct a critical text. In recent years, and for a large part owing to the application of computational methods, collation has evolved from auxiliary task to an active field of research. This paper addresses three critical obstacles confronting researchers in this field: the lack of a shared vocabulary to describe textual variation, the limited interoperability of collation tools and results, and the lack of informative visualizations of the collation output. Each of those will be briefly discussed below, followed by our proposed means of addressing them through international collaboration in the context of a scientific Lorentz workshop and a working group.

McLoad is far from the first scholar who invented a tool to help him compare text versions: the practice of collation dates back to the ancient libraries of Alexandria and Pergamon. Over the course of centuries, scholars have developed a variety of methodologies and techniques to facilitate the collation process, such as a strategic positioning of the different versions,¹ using so-called Optical or Mechanical Collators (Smith 2000, 2002), and experimenting with diff algorithms. The earliest automated collation tools date from the 1960s (see Nury and Spadini 2020, 3) and their development continues to this day. At first glance, calculating the differences between multiple versions of a text and aligning these texts on points where they agree seems relatively easy to compute, e.g., by applying the aforementioned diff algorithms. But cultural texts are fluid objects that often have complex properties, such as discontinuity, simultaneity,

¹ See for instance the painting by Cenni di Francesco of St. Jerome, patron of biblical textual scholars (https://matthiesengallery.com/work_of_art/saint-jerome-copying-sacred-texts).

non-linearity, or multiple levels of revision (Bleeker et al. 2019). What is more, cultural texts come on different carriers, from ancient papyri scrolls to hard drives, and each carrier type brings about its own particularities and challenges. In short, collation is a typical digital humanities research topic, which offers no lack of challenges to engage textual scholars as well as information specialists and computer scientists.

The past four decades, in particular, have witnessed a rapid development of computational tools and methods to improve the collation process. Tools such as Collate (Robinson 1989), CollateX,² Stemmaweb,³ MEDITE,⁴ and LERA⁵ have revolutionized the way scholars compare texts by eradicating the need to manually reconcile and identify changes between versions of a text. Yet some persistent challenges remain. First, the lack of a shared vocabulary to talk about textual variation. Traditionally, there is not one research methodology of collation; rather, there exists a variety of scholarly practices that are influenced by geographical and periodical factors. For example, for the comparison of the versions of Anne Frank's diary, scholars distinguished different levels of similarity ("identical", "similar", "semantically related"; see Bleeker et al. 2022), while scholars studying the versions of Dante's *Commedia* focus on linguistic categories (Tempestini and Spadini 2019), and the textual variation between versions of *The Martian* is classified using categories like "minor expansion" and "major condensation" (Ketzan and Schöch, 2021). The current situation makes it difficult to reach the level of abstraction required for building generic models and collation software.

A second challenge is that the visualizations of collation results are usually designed for and contained within a research project, for specific types of texts (e.g., the New Testament), particular authors (e.g., Goethe, Charles Harpur), or specific genres and/or time periods (e.g., 18th-century poetry). This "siloed" approach makes it difficult to replicate or share the analyses of textual variation on these platforms. It hinders comparative analyses, and makes it challenging for scholars to understand, assess, and review the collation results produced by their peers. Furthermore, there is a high risk of duplicating work – "new techniques [...] are designed while appropriate, sophisticated visualizations unrelated to digital humanities data already exist" (Jänicke et al. 2017, 241) – or even tunnel vision, resulting in "a high number of redundant tools solving one and the same issue" (Yousef and Jänicke 2020). Establishing standardized ways to report on and share the collation output would not only promote comparative analyses across literary genres or time periods, it would also work towards the

² <https://collatex.net>.

³ <https://stemmaweb.net/>.

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https://iscd.sorbonne-universite.fr/research/incubated-teams/digital-humanities/textual_iconographic_corpora/m edite/.

⁵ <https://lera.uzi.uni-halle.de/?lang=en>

development of interoperable and sustainable visualization tools. Finding agreement on file formats of collation output, for example, would ensure that visualization tools can be more easily adopted by multiple research projects, or incorporated into existing collation tools.

A third and final challenge is the design of effective visualizations of textual variation. Considering the variety of textual sources (ranging from different time periods to different authorial styles) as well as the different aims of collation (establishing a critical text, examining a text's genesis, or exploring its transmission), there currently exists at least an equal variety of visualizations. Prevalent visualizations of collation output are an alignment table and a variant graph. Both present a close reading of textual variation, producing a highly-detailed output which is, in all its scholarly detail, hard to comprehend and often unintelligible to non-experts. Barring a few exceptions (Elli et al. 2023, Jänicke and Wrisley 2017), most visualizations stay inside the realm of close reading, despite the research done in the area of distant reading visualizations for humanities research (e.g., Sinclair et al. 2013; McGarry 2020; Radzikowska and Ruecker 2021). There have been little to no usability studies done in this area (Jänicke et al. 2017), even though the diversity of the field and the various backgrounds of the users of collation tools would dictate otherwise. Overall, there exists as of yet no agreement on what constitutes an effective and informative visualization of collation output.

To address these challenges, we organised an international workshop on visualising textual variation, bringing together a wide and diverse group of experts with backgrounds in textual scholarship, collation software, information visualization, and knowledge organization. The workshop was organized in the context of the Lorentz Center,⁶ which promotes scholarly exchange, and took place from 14 to 17 April 2025. The core objectives of the workshop were (1) to develop standardized vocabularies for classifying textual variation in literary works; (2) to create guidelines and principles for sharing and publishing collation results; and (3) to inventory the requirements and design principles for visualizing textual variation. To safeguard the results of the workshop and to ensure a continued development of the standards, the workshop will also establish a Working Group concerned with maintaining community standards and guidelines for visualization of textual variation. In this paper we will present the workshop outcomes: we will give a detailed account of our approach to developing the shared vocabulary of textual variation, highlighting five key concepts understood differently across contexts, and present the design principles for sharing and publishing collation results elaborated during the workshop. Finally, and perhaps not surprisingly, we will end our presentation with a call to the DHBenelux community to subscribe to the Working Group, which can only succeed if maintained and supported by our community as a whole.

⁶ See the workshop website: <https://www.lorentzcenter.nl/seeing-the-difference-visualizing-textual-variation.html>.

The visualization of textual variation holds significant potential not only as a research tool for experts, but also as a way to communicate findings to a broader, non-specialist audience. It can reveal the evolving nature of a text, shedding light on its creation and development over time, and demonstrating that texts are not static objects, but living, changing entities. Following Randall McLoad's statement — "I love the process of collating" — the aim of the workshop, the Working Group, and our oral presentation at the DH Benelux is to embrace McLoad's enthusiasm and broaden access to automated collation research. Rather than being confined to a small group of specialists, we want to make this method a standard approach for analyzing and sharing textual variation across disciplines.

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